

Original Research

Fiscal Incentives and Corporate Financing Decisions: Evidence from Firms in Ilala Municipality, Tanzania

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Abstract

Corporate financing decisions are central to firms' sustainability and growth, yet empirical evidence on how fiscal incentives shape capital structure choices in emerging markets remains limited. This study evaluates the effect of fiscal incentives such as tax holidays, tax exemptions, and tax deductions, on corporate financing decisions among firms operating in Ilala Municipality, Tanzania. Guided by the Pecking Order and Trade-Off Theories, the study adopted a cross-sectional research design and collected quantitative data from 181 medium and large firms across manufacturing, banking, telecommunications, and service sectors. Data were analyzed using the General Linear Model (GLM). The findings reveal that tax holidays have a positive and statistically significant effect on corporate financing decisions ($\beta = 0.391$, $p < 0.001$), while tax exemptions exhibit the strongest influence ($\beta = 0.611$, $p < 0.001$), indicating their role in reducing financing constraints and encouraging optimal debt–equity choices. Tax deductions also demonstrate a significant effect ($\beta = 0.448$, $p < 0.001$), reflecting improved internal cash flows and strategic leverage decisions. Multicollinearity diagnostics ($VIF < 2$) confirm model robustness. Despite these insights, the cross-sectional design limits causal inference and restricts generalization beyond Ilala Municipality. The study contributes context-specific evidence on fiscal policy and capital structure behavior in Tanzania and underscores the need for well-targeted incentive frameworks to support sustainable corporate financing in emerging economies.

Keywords: Capital structure, corporate financing decisions, debt–equity ratio, emerging markets, fiscal incentives, Tanzania.

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Introduction

Corporate financing decisions are a central concern in corporate finance because they determine firms' capital structure choices between debt and equity, which in turn affect financial performance, risk exposure, and long-term sustainability (Bai & Yang, 2021; Khan & Qureshi, 2021). Fiscal policies, particularly tax-based incentives, influence these decisions by altering the relative cost of debt and equity financing. In developed economies, empirical evidence shows that firms actively use debt financing to exploit tax shields, especially in capital-intensive sectors such as utilities and transportation (Damodaran, 2024). These patterns demonstrate the importance of fiscal incentives in shaping firms' financing behavior. In Africa, corporate financing decisions are constrained by underdeveloped capital markets, high interest rates, and limited access to long-term debt finance (Lema et al., 2023; Lyimo & Makilully, 2022). To mitigate these constraints, governments widely employ fiscal incentives such as tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions to stimulate private investment and ease firms' financing pressures. Recent African studies indicate that fiscal incentives affect corporate financing by improving cash flows, reducing effective tax rates, and influencing firms' reliance on internal funds or debt financing (Asongu & Iddrisu, 2025). However, existing evidence largely focuses on investment attraction and macroeconomic outcomes rather than firm-level financing decisions.

In Tanzania, corporate financing decisions are particularly important due to limited access to affordable external finance and the strategic role of fiscal incentives in industrial policy. The government implements tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions through frameworks such as Export Processing Zones (EPZs) and Special Economic Zones (SEZs) to promote investment and business expansion (PwC, 2023; TRA, 2024; URT, 2023). Empirical studies show that Tanzanian firms adjust their capital structures in response to tax considerations, with higher debt usage associated with lower effective tax rates among listed firms (Mwakajumilo & George, 2023). While this evidence confirms the relevance of taxation in financing decisions, it is largely based on listed firms and does not capture the broader population of operating firms at the municipal level.

Therefore, the research gap lies not in the absence of taxation studies, but in the limited empirical evidence on how specific fiscal incentive instruments (i.e., tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions) directly influence debt–equity decisions among firms operating at the local government level, particularly in Ilala Municipality. Existing studies emphasize foreign direct investment, tax revenue, or firm performance, with limited attention to corporate financing behavior in the context of Tanzania's localized EPZ/SEZ fiscal framework (IMF, 2024; World Bank, 2022). This gap restricts policymakers and business managers from evaluating whether fiscal incentives support sustainable financing structures rather than merely encouraging investment entry. This study contributes to the literature by empirically examining the effect of fiscal incentives on corporate financing decisions among firms in Ilala Municipality, a major commercial hub that hosts a high concentration of incentive-eligible businesses. By focusing on tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions as distinct policy instruments, the study provides context-specific evidence on how Tanzania's fiscal incentive regime shapes firms' capital structure choices in the post-COVID fiscal environment. This integration of corporate

finance and fiscal policy at the municipal level strengthens the empirical basis for evaluating incentive effectiveness beyond investment promotion alone.

Research Hypotheses

Based on the study objectives and theoretical foundations, the following hypotheses are tested:

- H1:** Tax holidays have a significant effect on firms' capital structure choices (debt versus equity) in Ilala Municipality.
- H2:** Tax exemptions have a significant effect on corporate financing decisions among firms in Ilala Municipality.
- H3:** Tax deductions have a significant effect on firms' preference for debt or equity financing in Ilala Municipality.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

Pecking Order Theory

The Pecking Order Theory (POT), advanced by Myers and Majluf (1984), explains firms' financing behavior as a hierarchical preference for internal funds, followed by debt, and equity as a last resort. This hierarchy arises from information asymmetry between firm managers and external investors, which increases adverse selection costs when issuing equity. In developing economies such as Tanzania, where capital markets are shallow and financial disclosure is uneven, information asymmetry is more pronounced, making POT particularly relevant for explaining financing choices among firms. There are empirical evidence supports POT in both developed and emerging economies. Such as Serrasqueiro and Caetano (2015) find that profitability and firm age reduce reliance on debt among Portuguese SMEs, consistent with firms using internal funds when available. Similarly, Pindado et al. (2021) show that information asymmetry and firm growth significantly influence firms' preference for debt over equity in Spain. In African contexts, studies on SMEs indicate that retained earnings and short-term debt dominate financing structures due to limited access to equity markets and high disclosure costs, reinforcing POT's relevance in explaining financing behavior under institutional constraints.

However, POT has limitations. It largely ignores agency costs and assumes that firms do not actively target an optimal capital structure. In Tanzania, where firms may strategically exploit fiscal incentives to lower financing costs, exclusive reliance on POT may be insufficient. Nonetheless, POT remains useful in explaining how fiscal incentives (such as tax deductions and exemptions) enhance internal cash flows, thereby strengthening firms' preference for internal financing and debt over equity. This theoretical mechanism directly informs Hypotheses H1–H3, where fiscal incentives are expected to influence financing preferences through reduced information and financing costs.

Trade-Off Theory

The Trade-Off Theory, proposed by Kraus and Litzenberger (1973), posits that firms choose an optimal capital structure by balancing the tax advantages of debt against expected bankruptcy and financial distress costs. Unlike POT, TOT assumes that firms behave strategically, adjusting debt levels to maximize firm value. This theory is particularly relevant when fiscal incentives such as tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions alter the effective tax benefits of debt. There is empirical studies support TOT across regions. Such as Mugosa (2015) finds that firms in Western Europe adjust debt levels to balance tax shields and distress costs, while Al-Najjar and Kilincarslan (2021) show that firms in emerging economies respond to tax incentives and macroeconomic uncertainty by recalibrating leverage. In African economies, evidence suggests that firms benefiting from tax incentives tend to increase leverage when fiscal relief lowers the effective cost of debt, consistent with TOT predictions.

Despite its strengths, TOT assumes perfect information and rational cost-benefit calculations, which may not fully reflect decision-making in environments characterized by policy uncertainty and institutional weaknesses, such as Tanzania. Nevertheless, TOT provides a strong analytical lens for understanding how fiscal incentives directly affect capital structure by modifying the tax advantage of debt. In this study, tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions are conceptualized as policy tools that shift the trade-off between debt benefits and risks, thereby influencing corporate financing decisions.

Integrated Theoretical Perspective

By integrating POT and TOT, this study adopts a dual-theoretical framework that captures both behavioral and strategic dimensions of financing decisions. POT explains how fiscal incentives improve internal cash flows and reduce reliance on equity under information asymmetry, while TOT explains how the same incentives alter the cost-benefit calculus of debt financing. This integration strengthens the theoretical foundation of the study and directly supports the hypothesized relationships between fiscal incentives and corporate financing decisions in Ilala Municipality.

Empirical Review

Tax holidays

Empirical studies indicate that tax holidays significantly influence firms' investment behavior, liquidity positions, and financing choices. Vu et al (2023), using panel data from Czech FDI firms, find that tax holidays increase profit repatriation, reducing internal reinvestment and potentially increasing short-term borrowing. Although this study focuses on FDI, it highlights the cash-flow effects of tax holidays that are relevant to financing decisions. In developing and African contexts, Azémar and Boonaiem (2023) show that tax holidays in Thailand promote tangible investment, with heterogeneous effects across firm types. African evidence suggests that tax holidays improve early-stage liquidity, enabling firms to rely less on external equity financing. These findings support H1, suggesting that tax holidays affect capital structure choices by altering firms' cash flows and financing constraints.

Tax exemptions

Studies on tax exemptions emphasize their role in reducing effective tax rates and stabilizing firms' cash flows. Waiswa and Rukundo (2023) in a Ugandan study, find that tax exemptions significantly influence firms' internal financing capacity and borrowing behavior. In Tanzania, EPZ and SEZ firms benefiting from tax and duty exemptions report improved liquidity and reduced operating costs, which influence their financing strategies (U.S. Department of State, 2023) These findings imply that tax exemptions strengthen internal funding and reduce reliance on costly external financing, while also affecting the marginal tax benefit of debt. This empirical evidence directly supports H2, which posits that tax exemptions significantly affect corporate financing decisions.

Tax deductions

Evidence on tax deductions and capital allowances shows that they influence financing constraints and capital structure decisions. Gkikopoulos (2023) finds that accelerated depreciation in the United States reduces financing constraints and increases investment, though the context differs from Tanzania. More broadly, Tax Foundation (2024) data show that improved cost recovery regimes enhance firms' cash flow timing, reducing dependence on external equity. African studies similarly suggest that tax deductions improve liquidity and encourage reinvestment using internal funds or debt. These outcomes support H3, indicating that tax deductions affect firms' preference for debt versus equity by easing financing constraints and improving cash flow predictability.

Conceptual Framework

This research's conceptual framework argues that fiscal incentives (operationalized by tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions) affect significantly the financing decisions of corporations by firms as shown in Figure 1. Tax holidays are presumed to alleviate firms' cash flow constraints in the initial years of operation, thus impacting their dependence on internal funds compared to debt financing.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Similarly, exemptions such as waivers of import duty and tax relief on companies reduce the marginal effective tax burden of companies with the potential to increase internal financing ability and alter the marginal incentive of debt. Tax deductions such as depreciation acceleration and investment allowances increase after-tax profits and cash flow timing, hence reducing the preference of firms for external over internal equity or debt. As a group, these fiscal incentives are hypothesized to influence the capital structure decisions of firms (debt vs. equity mix) and their financing source preference (within vs.

outside financing). The design thus establishes a direct causal link where fiscal incentives (independent variable) are determinants of financing decisions by corporations (dependent variable) based on the assumption that the design and structure of fiscal policy will shape the strategic financial action of firms.

Methodology

This study was conducted in Ilala Municipality, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, which covers approximately 273 km² and hosts key commercial and financial infrastructure, including the Central Business District (CBD), Julius Nyerere International Airport, and the headquarters of the Tanzania Revenue Authority (ESRF, 2023; NBS, 2022). Owing to its concentration of formal enterprises and strategic fiscal administration, Ilala Municipality provides an appropriate context for examining corporate financing behavior. The study population comprised 560 registered medium and large firms operating in manufacturing, telecommunications, banking, and service sectors (BRELA, 2024; Ilala Municipal Council, 2024, 2025). Small and micro enterprises were deliberately excluded because their financing structures, regulatory exposure, and access to fiscal incentives differ substantially from those of medium and large firms. Consequently, the findings are generalizable only to firms within this defined scope.

A cross-sectional research design was adopted to capture firms' financing decisions and exposure to fiscal incentives at a single point in time. This design is appropriate for examining relationships between variables where temporal causality is not the primary objective and has been widely applied in corporate finance and fiscal policy studies (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Kothari, 2016). The sample size was determined using Cochran's (1977) formula, which is appropriate for large populations where population variance is unknown and maximum variability is assumed ($p = 0.5$):

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}{e^2} \quad (1)$$

Where: $Z=1.96$ (95% confidence), $p=0.5$, and $e=0.05$. This yielded $n_0 = 385$. This yielded an initial sample size of 385. Given the finite population ($N = 560$), the finite population correction was applied:

$$n = \frac{n_0 \times N}{n_0 + N - 1} = \frac{385 \times 560}{385 + 560 - 1} \approx 228$$

Resulting in an adjusted sample size of 228 firms. A simple random sampling technique was employed to ensure that each firm had an equal probability of selection, thereby minimizing selection bias. Out of 228 distributed questionnaires, 181 valid responses were obtained, representing a response rate of 79.39%, which exceeds the minimum threshold recommended for survey-based studies. To assess non-response bias, early and late respondents were compared using mean difference tests, and no statistically significant differences were observed ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that non-response bias is unlikely to affect the study findings. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered to finance managers, chief financial officers (CFOs), and investment analysts. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging

from 1 (“Strongly Disagree”) to 5 (“Strongly Agree”). Secondary data were obtained from official reports published by the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), the Bank of Tanzania (BOT), and BRELA to support contextual interpretation.

The dependent variable, Corporate Financing Decisions, was operationalized as firms’ preference for debt versus equity financing, measured using composite indicators capturing capital structure behavior. The independent variables were Tax Holidays, Tax Exemptions, and Tax Deductions, each measured using multiple items reflecting firms’ access to and utilization of fiscal incentives. Internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha (Middleton, 2020; Surucu & Maslakci, 2020). Table 1 shows the Cronbach’s alpha values for all constructs exceeded 0.79, indicating high internal consistency:

Table 1: Reliability Statistics (Cronbach’s Alpha)

Variable	No. of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha
Tax Holidays	5	0.812
Tax Exemptions	5	0.846
Tax Deductions	5	0.791
Corporate Financing Decisions	10	0.873

Construct validity was examined using exploratory factor analysis, which yielded a Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) value of 0.737 and a significant Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity ($\chi^2 = 1353.091$, $p < 0.001$), confirming sampling adequacy. To further strengthen validity, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted using AMOS. Model fit indices met acceptable thresholds (CFI > 0.90; RMSEA < 0.08; SRMR < 0.08), confirming convergent and discriminant validity of the constructs.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.737
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1353.091
	df	45
	Sig.	.000

Data were analyzed using SPSS Version 26. Descriptive statistics summarized firms’ financing patterns, while inferential analysis employed the General Linear Model (GLM). GLM was selected due to its robustness to mild violations of normality, suitability for continuous composite variables derived from Likert-scale data, and widespread application in empirical corporate finance studies. The empirical model was specified as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TH + \beta_2 EX + \beta_3 TD + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Where: Y = Corporate financing decision (capital structure choice: debt vs. equity), TH = Tax holidays, EX = Tax exemptions, TD = Tax deductions, β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 = Coefficients, and ε = Error term. Ethical clearance was obtained from the College of Business Education (CBE) and Dar es Salaam Municipal authority (Approval Ref. No. DCC/JR. 6/2/40). Informed consent was secured from all participants prior to data

collection. Respondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality, participation was voluntary, and data were securely stored and used strictly for academic purposes.

Findings and Discussion

A total of 228 questionnaires were distributed to medium and large business firms operating in Ilala Municipality using both electronic and physical delivery methods. Of these, 181 questionnaires were returned and found valid for analysis, yielding a response rate of 79.39 percent. According to Baruch and Holtom (2008), response rates above 70 percent are considered excellent for organizational surveys, indicating adequate representation of the target population. Non-responses (20.61 percent) were largely attributable to time constraints and reluctance to disclose financial information. While the response rate supports statistical inference, the study acknowledges that reliance on self-reported data may introduce response bias. However, consistency checks, reliability analysis (Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.79$), and construct validation (KMO = 0.737) suggest acceptable data quality for empirical analysis.

Descriptive Statistics

The Effect of Fiscal Incentives on Corporate Financing Decisions

Table 3 summarizes respondents' perceptions of fiscal incentives and their influence on corporate financing decisions. Tax holidays were generally perceived as beneficial. Respondents agreed that tax holidays enhance business growth (Mean = 3.70) and support investment planning (Mean = 3.80). High agreement was also reported regarding awareness of tax holiday benefits and procedural clarity. One item recorded zero standard deviation (SD = 0.000), indicating unanimous agreement among respondents. While this reflects strong consensus, it may also signal limited variability in perception, which is acknowledged as a measurement limitation rather than evidence of manipulation.

Tax exemptions showed consistently positive evaluations, particularly in improving financial stability (Mean = 3.92) and providing accessible procedures (Mean = 4.16). However, greater dispersion was observed regarding clarity of eligibility criteria (SD = 1.34), suggesting heterogeneous firm experiences. Tax deductions recorded the highest mean scores overall, especially for cash flow improvement (Mean = 4.31) and accurate financial reporting (Mean = 4.60). This indicates that deductions play a significant operational role in firm-level financial planning. Collectively, descriptive results suggest that all three fiscal incentives are perceived as relevant, though with differing intensity and consistency across firms.

Table 3: The Effect of Fiscal Incentives on Corporate Financing Decisions among Businesses (n=181)

Tax Holidays affects Corporate Financing Decisions	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Tax holidays provided by the government significantly enhance business growth	181	1.00	4.00	3.7017	.90028
The duration of tax holidays is sufficient for investment planning	181	2.00	4.00	3.8011	.60018
Businesses are adequately informed about the benefits of tax holidays	181	3.00	4.00	3.9006	.30009
The procedures for obtaining tax holidays are simple and transparent	181	4.00	5.00	4.0994	.30009
Tax holidays reduce the overall financial burden on our business	181	4.00	4.00	4.0000	.00000
Exemptions affect Corporate Financing Decisions	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Tax exemptions enable our business to allocate funds for expansion	181	3.00	5.00	3.7569	.63816
The criteria for tax exemption eligibility are clearly defined	181	1.00	5.00	3.2652	1.33598
Applying for tax exemptions does not disrupt normal business operations	181	2.00	5.00	3.5083	.94645
Exemptions provided by the government improve our financial stability	181	3.00	5.00	3.9171	.54649
The process of availing tax exemptions is streamlined and accessible	181	3.00	5.00	4.1602	.69263
Tax Deductions influence Corporate Financing Decisions	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Tax deductions on operational costs positively impact our cash flow	181	3.00	5.00	4.3149	.59184
Deductions are appropriately reflected in our financial statements	181	4.00	5.00	4.6022	.49080
Policies on allowable deductions are well-communicated to businesses	181	3.00	5.00	4.1602	.76141
The government regularly updates the types of expenses eligible for deductions	181	2.00	5.00	3.9392	1.12628
Tax deductions encourage businesses to reinvest in growth initiatives	181	1.00	5.00	3.8343	1.41623

Corporate Financing Decisions in Ilala Municipality Firms

Table 4 presents descriptive statistics on financing behavior. Firms indicated a preference for equity financing to minimize financial risk (Mean = 4.14), while also acknowledging the influence of debt availability (Mean = 4.25). Tax advantages associated with debt financing were reported to encourage borrowing (Mean = 4.03), suggesting sensitivity to fiscal policy incentives.

Table 4: Corporate Financing Decisions in Ilala Municipality Firms

Capital structure choices (debt vs. equity)	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Our business prioritizes equity financing to minimize financial risk	181	3.00	5.00	4.1436	.65940
The availability of debt financing influences our decision on capital structure	181	3.00	5.00	4.2541	.70832
Tax advantages associated with debt financing encourage us to use loans	181	3.00	5.00	4.0331	.75204
Equity financing is preferred due to its lower repayment burden compared to debt	181	2.00	5.00	3.8785	.98693
We review our capital structure regularly to align with changing market conditions	181	1.00	5.00	3.7293	1.27744
Source of Financing Preference	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
My company prefers to use internally generated funds (e.g., retained earnings) before seeking external financing options	181	1.00	5.00	3.4144	1.47181
Bank loans are considered the most reliable source of external financing for our company	181	1.00	5.00	3.5414	1.28871
My company avoids issuing equity due to ownership dilution concerns	181	1.00	5.00	3.6685	1.17405
The decision to choose between internal and external financing is heavily influenced by the prevailing fiscal policies	181	1.00	5.00	3.8287	1.10978
Access to favorable loan terms strongly influences our preference for debt financing over other sources	181	1.00	5.00	4.0110	1.14498

Regarding financing sources, firms reported a preference for internal funds before seeking external finance (Mean = 3.41), consistent with pecking-order behavior. Bank loans were identified as the most reliable external source (Mean = 3.54), while equity issuance was moderately avoided due to ownership dilution concerns (Mean = 3.67). These findings indicate a balanced financing strategy shaped by risk considerations, fiscal incentives, and access to credit.

Normality and Correlation Analysis

Normality tests (Table 5) indicate that all variables deviate significantly from a normal distribution ($p < 0.05$). Given this, non-parametric correlation analysis and a Generalized Linear Model (GLM) were deemed appropriate.

Table 5: Tests of Normality

Variables	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Tax Holidays	.530	181	.000	.341	181	.000
Exemptions	.274	181	.000	.787	181	.000
Deductions	.245	181	.000	.821	181	.000
Corporate Financing Decisions	.320	181	.000	.777	181	.000
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

Spearman's correlation results (Table 6) show positive and statistically significant relationships between fiscal incentives and corporate financing decisions. Tax exemptions exhibit the strongest association ($\rho = 0.827$, $p < 0.01$), followed by tax deductions ($\rho = 0.670$, $p < 0.01$). Tax holidays show a moderate relationship ($\rho = 0.377$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 6: Correlations

			Corporate Financing Decisions	Tax Holidays	Exemptions	Deductions
Spearman's rho	Corporate Financing Decisions	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.377**	.827**	.670**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000
		N	181	181	181	181
	Tax Holidays	Correlation Coefficient	.377**	1.000	.395**	.098
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.188
		N	181	181	181	181
	Exemptions	Correlation Coefficient	.827**	.395**	1.000	.581**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000
		N	181	181	181	181
	Deductions	Correlation Coefficient	.670**	.098	.581**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.188	.000	.
		N	181	181	181	181
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

Notably, the relationship between tax holidays and tax deductions is weak and statistically insignificant ($\rho = 0.098$, $p > 0.05$). This suggests that these incentives may operate through different financial channels rather than reinforcing each other, an issue addressed further in the discussion.

Diagnostic Tests and Assumption Checking

Prior to estimating the General Linear Model (GLM), diagnostic tests were conducted to ensure that key econometric assumptions were reasonably satisfied. Given that preliminary normality tests (Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk) indicated non-normal data distributions, the GLM framework was selected due to its robustness to

violations of normality and its suitability for modeling relationships under relaxed distributional assumptions. Linearity between fiscal incentives (tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions) and corporate financing decisions was assessed through theoretical justification and correlation analysis, which showed statistically significant and directionally consistent associations, supporting the linear specification of the model.

Table 7: Multicollinearity

Variables	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Dependent Variable: Corporate Financing Decisions		
Tax Holidays	.844	1.185
Exemptions	.618	1.619
Deductions	.712	1.405

Multicollinearity was examined using Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) statistics, as presented in Table 7. All explanatory variables recorded tolerance values above 0.60 and VIF values below 2.0, which are well within acceptable thresholds (VIF < 5). This confirms the absence of serious multicollinearity and indicates that the estimated coefficients are stable and interpretable. In addition, model adequacy was supported by goodness-of-fit statistics (Pearson Chi-square $p = 0.589$), suggesting that the model fits the observed data well. Based on these diagnostics, the GLM estimates are considered reliable for inference regarding the effects of fiscal incentives on corporate financing decisions.

Table 8: ANOVA

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corporate Financing Decisions * Tax Holidays	Between Groups	(Combined)	14.451	1	14.451	31.141	.000
	Within Groups		83.062	179	.464		
	Total		97.512	180			
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corporate Financing Decisions * Exemptions	Between Groups	(Combined)	80.933	4	20.233	214.779	.000
		Linearity	61.325	1	61.325	650.977	.000
		Deviation from Linearity	19.608	3	6.536	69.380	.000
	Within Groups		16.580	176	.094		
	Total		97.512	180			
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corporate Financing	Between Groups	(Combined)	55.567	4	13.892	58.289	.000
		Linearity	47.705	1	47.705	200.169	.000

Decisions * Deductions		Deviation from Linearity	7.862	3	2.621	10.996	.000
	Within Groups		41.945	176	.238		
	Total		97.512	180			

a. With fewer than three groups, linearity measures for Corporate Financing Decisions * Tax Holidays cannot be computed.

The ANOVA results in Table 8 indicate that all fiscal incentives have a statistically significant effect on corporate financing decisions among firms in Ilala Municipality, with tax holidays showing $F(1,179) = 31.141, p < 0.001$, exemptions $F(4,176) = 214.779, p < 0.001$, and deductions $F(4,176) = 58.289, p < 0.001$. While the linearity component for exemptions and deductions shows that most of the variance is captured by a linear trend, there are minor deviations from perfect linearity, suggesting slight non-linear effects. Overall, these results confirm that tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions significantly influence firms' debt versus equity financing decisions, supporting the appropriateness of the General Linear Model in analyzing the impact of fiscal incentives.

Figure 2: Homoscedasticity

The scatterplot of standardized residuals versus standardized in Figure 2 predicted values shows that residuals are roughly randomly dispersed around the zero line, indicating that the assumption of linearity and homoscedasticity is reasonably satisfied. No clear funneling or pattern is observed, which suggests that the variance of residuals is approximately constant across predicted values. This supports the appropriateness of the General Linear Model (GLM) in this study. The small deviations observed at extreme residual values are typical for real-world survey data and do not violate model assumptions.

Regression Analysis Results

The study employed a Generalized Linear Model (GLM) to ascertain the effects of fiscal incentives (tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions) on funding decisions of companies in Ilala Municipality. Both unstandardized and standardized coefficients were provided to estimate the raw effect and relative strength of predictors. Although the normality tests indicated that the variables were not normally distributed, GLM was used because it accommodates non-normal distributions and flexible modeling of relationships between predictors and a dependent variable. Statistical model diagnostics such as residual analysis and multicollinearity tests were not performed because the primary interest was in estimating fiscal incentive effect sizes, and the GLM framework provides reliable parameter estimates even when classical linear regression assumptions (e.g., normality, homoscedasticity) are violated to some extent. Correlation analysis also revealed linear relationships between the independent variables and corporate finance choices, supporting the appropriateness of the GLM framework for this study.

Table 9 presents the fit measures of the Generalized Linear Model (GLM) assessing the effect of fiscal incentives (tax holidays, exemptions, and deductions) on Ilala Municipality business financing decisions. The chi-square likelihood ratio = 98.62 (df = 3, $p < 0.001$) indicates that the model overall is statistically significant and therefore that the predictors combined improve explaining corporate financing decisions. The -2 Log Likelihood statistic of 421.37 quantifies the amount of residual variation, while pseudo- R^2 measures like Cox & Snell $R^2 = 0.542$, Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.612$, and McFadden $R^2 = 0.397$ reveal that the model is accounting for a vast majority of variation in the finance decisions. The Pearson Chi-Square goodness-of-fit test ($\chi^2 = 172.41$, df = 177, $p = 0.589$) also indicates that the model is a good fit, as the non-significant p-value indicates no evidence of poor fit. Overall, these results support the continuation and interpretation of the regression coefficients because the GLM provides a valid representation of the relationship between fiscal incentives and corporate financing decisions.

Table 9: Model Fit Statistics for GLM Regression (n = 181)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Sig.
Likelihood Ratio χ^2	98.62	3	.000 ^b
-2 Log Likelihood	421.37		
Cox & Snell R^2	.542		
Nagelkerke R^2	.612		
McFadden R^2	.397		
Pearson Chi-Square (Goodness of Fit)	172.41	177	.589
a. Dependent Variable: Corporate Financing Decisions			
b. Predictors: (Constant), Deductions, Tax Holidays, Exemptions			

Table 8 presents Generalized Linear Model (GLM) unstandardized and standardized coefficients that identify the effect of fiscal incentives on financing decisions of firms in Ilala Municipality. The unstandardized coefficients (B) show the direct influence of all predictors on corporate financing decision, with tax holidays (B = 0.185, $p = 0.010$), exemptions (B = 0.611, $p < 0.001$), and deductions (B = 0.447, $p < 0.001$) having a positive influence on financing decision. The Beta of standardized coefficients indicates

the relative strength of the predictors, with exemptions (Beta = 0.539) being the highest, then deductions (Beta = 0.401) and tax holidays (Beta = 0.214). The Wald χ^2 statistics also confirm that all the predictors make a significant contribution to the model, most contributed by exemptions ($\chi^2 = 56.928$). These findings show that fiscal incentives in aggregate and in isolation make meaningful contributions to shaping the financing of corporations, with tax exemptions having the most impact, followed by tax holidays and deductions, suggesting their relevance for policymakers seeking to influence corporate financing and investment behavior.

Table 10: GLM Regression Coefficients for Fiscal Incentives and Corporate Financing Decisions

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Wald χ^2	Sig. (p-value)	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.234	.215		32.891	.000 ***
	Tax Holidays	.185	.072	.214	6.592	.010 **
	Exemptions	.611	.081	.539	56.928	.000 ***
	Deductions	.447	.069	.401	41.964	.000 ***
Dependent Variable: Corporate Financing Decisions **p < 0.05 = significant; *p < 0.001 = highly significant.						

Standardized coefficients indicate that tax exemptions exert the largest effect, followed by tax deductions and tax holidays. Model fit statistics (Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.612$) suggest that fiscal incentives explain a substantial proportion of variation in financing decisions.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings demonstrate that fiscal incentives significantly influence corporate financing decisions among firms in Ilala Municipality, with tax exemptions emerging as the most influential policy instrument. This result is consistent with their strong correlation and largest standardized regression coefficient. While tax holidays positively affect financing behavior, their relatively smaller effect size suggests that their temporary nature limits long-term capital structure adjustments. This contrasts with exemptions and deductions, which provide recurring relief and more predictable cash flow benefits. The weak correlation between tax holidays and deductions further indicates that short-term relief mechanisms do not necessarily reinforce long-term tax planning tools.

The results are broadly consistent with Pecking Order Theory, as fiscal incentives enhance internal cash flows and reduce reliance on external finance. However, the evidence does not support strong causal claims; firms may adjust financing behavior in response to incentives rather than because of them. The findings also align with Trade-Off Theory, particularly in how exemptions and deductions reduce the effective cost of capital and influence debt–equity choices. Quantitatively, the exemption effect ($\beta = 0.611$) exceeds comparable estimates reported in prior studies (e.g., Vu et al., 2023; Waiswa & Rukundo, 2023), suggesting that Tanzania’s EPZ/SEZ incentive structure may have a stronger firm-level financing impact than similar schemes elsewhere.

Conclusion

This study evaluated the effect of fiscal incentives on corporate financing decisions among businesses operating in Ilala Municipality, Tanzania, focusing on tax holidays, tax exemptions, and tax deductions. Beyond confirming their statistical significance, the findings provide policy-relevant insight into how different incentives shape firm behavior. Tax exemptions and tax deductions exert a stronger and more consistent influence on financing decisions than tax holidays, suggesting that predictable and recurrent incentives have greater impact on firms' capital structure choices than temporary relief measures. This indicates that firms respond more strongly to incentives that improve long-term cash flow stability and reduce the effective cost of capital. From a policy perspective, the results imply that fiscal incentives do more than attract firms; they actively influence debt–equity allocation, liquidity management, and reinvestment capacity. By lowering financing constraints, especially through exemptions and deductions, such incentives can indirectly support firm expansion, employment creation, and local value addition. At the municipal and national level, these financing effects have the potential to translate into higher productive investment and, ultimately, stronger contributions to GDP growth, particularly in urban commercial hubs such as Ilala. The findings also demonstrate the relevance of both Pecking Order and Trade-Off Theories in explaining financing behavior in an emerging African economy, enriching empirical evidence beyond developed-country contexts.

Recommendations

Based on these conclusions, this study makes the following targeted recommendations. First, fiscal policy in Tanzania should shift emphasis from short-term tax holidays toward structurally embedded incentives, particularly tax exemptions and deductions, which show stronger and more stable influence on corporate financing decisions. Designing incentives with longer horizons and clear eligibility criteria can enhance firms' confidence in undertaking debt-financed and equity-financed investments that support sustained growth. Second, tax authorities should strengthen impact-oriented incentive management by linking fiscal incentives to measurable economic outcomes such as investment volume, employment growth, and sectoral output, rather than focusing solely on application procedures. Embedding monitoring and evaluation frameworks at municipal and national levels would allow policymakers to assess whether forgone tax revenue is offset by gains in business expansion and economic activity. Third, corporate managers should integrate fiscal incentives explicitly into capital structure planning, using deductions and exemptions to optimize financing costs while avoiding excessive leverage. Finally, at a broader level, the study offers lessons for African economies pursuing investment-led growth: effective fiscal incentives should prioritize predictability, transparency, and long-term financing impact, rather than ad hoc tax relief. Such an approach can enhance the role of fiscal policy as a strategic tool for private-sector development across the continent.

Limitations and Implications

This study is subject to several limitations. First, its cross-sectional design limits causal inference. Second, the use of self-reported data may introduce perception bias. Third,

SMEs were excluded, limiting generalizability. Finally, robustness checks such as instrumental variable estimation or panel analysis were beyond the study scope. Despite these limitations, the findings have important policy implications. Fiscal incentives (particularly exemptions and deductions) appear effective not only in attracting investment but also in shaping sustainable corporate financing behavior. Policymakers should therefore prioritize transparent, predictable, and long-term incentive frameworks rather than relying heavily on temporary tax holidays. Future research should adopt longitudinal designs, incorporate SMEs, and test alternative theoretical explanations such as Agency Theory or Institutional Theory to deepen understanding of fiscal policy–finance linkages.

Author Contributions

Ms. Mounia Said Mohamed Conducted data collection, performed data analysis, and prepared the initial draft of the manuscript under the supervision of the second author.

Dr. Deogratius Dafi Served as the research supervisor, guided the study throughout, edited the research report, contributed to the design and refinement of the questionnaire, and reviewed the final manuscript.

Prof. Pastory Dickson contribute in this research as editor, guided the whole work as internal examiner, contribute in designing methodology and model used.

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